

HEALTH-PRESERVING ACTIVITY OF STUDENTS IN PEDAGOGICAL UNIVERSITIES

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Abstract. *The article examines the phenomenon of health-preserving activity of students as an important component of their personal and professional development. Social activity is manifested through students' participation in various projects, practical tasks, research initiatives, volunteer actions, and socially significant events focused on the preservation and promotion of health. Such activity contributes to the formation of responsibility, initiative, teamwork skills, and a conscious attitude among young people toward their role in society in matters of health preservation.*

Keywords: *students, classes, health-preserving activity, volunteering, programs.*

Introduction

In the modern world, students' health is becoming an increasingly relevant issue, as the level of stress and psychological strain among young people has significantly increased. In this regard, physical culture plays an important role in maintaining students' health, contributing to both physical and mental well-being.[1]

Social activity, including health-preserving activity, during the student years is manifested in a new type of thinking and an individual perspective on the importance of preserving and strengthening both one's own health and the health of others. During this period, personal qualities are formed that determine an active life position of a young person, including awareness, the ability to respond adequately to challenging situations, the capacity to interact with others and regulate one's own behavior, as well as the desire to make responsible decisions in matters of public health preservation.[2]

One of the key factors in the formation of a healthy personality is the planning and implementation of life goals. For this reason, students actively engage in various types of activities, fully expressing their social activity, including participation in volunteering and education, which are closely interconnected and complement each other in the process of personal development. Participation in volunteer activities aimed at preserving public health benefits society and at the same time contributes to the development of important skills and qualities necessary for successful studies, future professional activity, and a healthy life in general. For students, volunteering becomes an opportunity to gain valuable experience, improve their abilities, and contribute to helping those in need. Such activity not only supports personal development but also helps to improve the surrounding world. Volunteering allows young people to feel useful and significant in the development of a healthy society. Participation in charitable events, assistance campaigns, and volunteer projects related to health issues increases students' self-esteem and motivation, stimulating their achievements in strengthening the health of others. [3]

Students can provide assistance to low-income populations, children, and the elderly, as well as participate in environmental and charitable projects. Volunteering fosters responsibility, empathy, and communication skills, and contributes to the formation of an active civic position. At our university, students are actively involved in the implementation of various projects. On April 18, 2025, the Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami hosted an international scientific and practical conference entitled “Innovative Education: Bridging the Gap between Technology and Traditional Education.” The conference was attended by specialists from more than ten foreign countries, who delivered presentations on international experience in improving the effectiveness of reforms in the field of pedagogy and on trends in the development of modern pedagogy. Students also participated in organizing the conference and delivered presentations, actively engaging in discussions. [4]

Students of the Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami are actively involved in friendship projects between Uzbekistan and Azerbaijan through the Uzbekistan–Azerbaijan Friendship Society. Within the framework of this cooperation, students take part in cultural events, exhibitions, and literary evenings.[5]

M. E. Lavrov, analyzing the history and theoretical approaches to students’ social activity, noted that activity is not merely participation, but an important characteristic reflecting students’ readiness to influence society and their surrounding environment. [6]

T. K. Mukhina identifies types and forms of social activity, considering it as an integral personal quality that includes pragmatic participation (social and professional) as well as value orientations.[7]

In the study by O. Latipova and N. Turakulova, it is stated that volunteering is the most important form of social activity for youth in the field of health preservation, as it contributes to the development of moral values, a sense of responsibility, and solidarity.[8] One of the key factors in engaging students is the availability of interesting and diverse programs designed with consideration of the interests and needs of the target audience. Such programs may include creative workshops, educational seminars, and social projects.

Modern students widely use digital technologies; therefore, engaging them through online platforms can significantly increase their level of participation in promoting a healthy lifestyle. It is recommended to use effective tools such as webinars and online courses, as well as mobile applications for organizing events. Involving students in the process of planning activities allows them to feel their importance and responsibility for preserving the health of others. This may include conducting surveys to identify students’ interests, creating working groups to develop new ideas, and involving students in organizing activities aimed at preserving and strengthening health.

Creative and health-preserving activity represents forms of students’ participation in various creative, artistic, and cultural initiatives. It is manifested through creative projects such as theatrical performances, concerts, literary competitions, art exhibitions, workshops, and art projects, as well as cultural events including festivals, flash mobs, cultural and educational projects, and participation in online cultural spaces and blog projects aimed at fostering a culture of health.

Special attention should be paid to the activities of Dominic Palmer, a climate justice activist. Dominic Palmer is a British student and activist who has dedicated her life to issues of climate justice and social responsibility. She studied political science and international relations at the University of Birmingham, and during her student years became actively involved in global environmental initiatives related to the issue of “Ecology and Health.” One of the key areas of her

activity is participation in School Strike for Climate, a movement of student climate strikes inspired by Greta Thunberg.[8]

Thus, students' social activity is manifested through various forms of participation in public life, including volunteering, practical and research projects, cultural and creative initiatives, participation in student associations, and civic projects. Scholars note that social activity contributes to the development of personal and professional qualities, fostering leadership, responsibility, communication and organizational skills, critical thinking, and a creative approach to problem-solving. It helps students achieve self-realization, integrate into a community, and perceive the significance of their actions and their impact on society.[9]

Participation of students in social, cultural, scientific, and practical initiatives is not only a form of self-realization, but also an important factor in the formation of a comprehensively developed, healthy personality prepared for professional and civic life.

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